

**AHMAD DONISHNING "MANG'ITLAR SULOLASI TARIXI"
ASARIDAGI IJTIMOIIY-SIYOIIY QARASHLAR**

**SOCIO-POLITICAL VIEWS IN AHMAD DONISH'S "HISTORY OF
THE MANGIT DYNASTY"**

**СОЦИАЛЬНО-ПОЛИТИЧЕСКИЕ ВЗГЛЯДЫ В «ИСТОРИИ
ДИНАСТИИ МАНГИТ» АХМАДА ДОНИША**

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**Buxoro davlat tibbiyot instituti Ijtimoiy fanlar kafedrasini mudiri,
dotsent PhD**

Аннотация: В данной статье, автор исследует социально-политические взгляды в историческом произведении Ахмада Дониша «Истории Мангытской династии», круг проблем и актуальные вопросы. Две работы Ахмада Дониша посвящены в основном проблемам истории и государственного управления. Это, прежде всего, «Навадир-уль-Ваке», который является основной и важнейшей частью «Политического трактата», и «он занимает первое место как по времени своего создания, так и по своему значению».

Abstract: In this article, the author explores the socio-political views in the historical work of Ahmad Donish "History of the Mangyt Dynasty", the range of problems and current issues. Two works by Ahmad Donish are devoted mainly to problems of history and public administration. This is, first of all, "Nawadir-ul-Waqe", which is the main and most important part of the "Political Treatise", and "it ranks first both in the time of its creation and in its significance."

Annotatsiya: Muallif ushbu maqolada Ahmad Donishning "Mang'itlar sulolasi tarixi" tarixiy asaridagi ijtimoiy-siyosiy qarashlar, muammolar doirasi va dolzarb masalalarni o'rganadi. Ahmad Donishning ikkita asari asosan tarix va davlat boshqaruvi muammolariga bag'ishlangan. Bu, avvalo, «Siyosiy risola»ning asosiy va eng muhim qismi bo'lgan «Navodir-ul-vaqe» bo'lib, «u yaratilish davrida ham, ahamiyati jihatidan ham birinchi o'rinda turadi».

Ключевые слова: династия, социальное положение, политический строй, описание, анализ, мангыты, историческое произведение

Tayanch so‘zlar: sulola, ijtimoiy mavqe, siyosiy tuzum, tavsif, tahlil, mang‘itlar, tarixiy asar

Key words: dynasty, social status, political system, description, analysis, mangyts, historical work

Currently, in the Bukhara State Museum-Reserve, Ahmad Donish's draft and original copy of "Mukhtasare az tarikhi sultanati khandano mangitiya" (written in the last years of his life) and "Navodirul waqoe" written by his own hand (i.e. the first book of 1880) is preserved.

The work "Mukhtasare az tarikhi sultanati khandoni mangitiya" dedicated to the history of Bukhara emirs (the book is also called "Risela" and "Tarikhcha") begins with the description of the planets, and in the following places Bukhara mangit management and military policy of the emirs, dedicated to memories of a trip to Russia. The original copy of this work, kept in the Bukhara Museum, has its own history. On September 26, 1959, this book was accepted into the oriental manuscripts fund of the museum by Ahmed Kasimzada, an employee of the Bukhara Museum. Muhiddinov from Bukhara donated the book to the museum. And the book was a souvenir from his grandfather Qazi Saidahmadi Bukhari. This can be seen from the two seals on the last pages of the book. At one time, Ahmadi was a close friend of Porina. In this regard, the author presented his work to the judge. The book consists of 48 pages and is written in the "shikasta" type of the nastalyq letter. The name of the work and the time of writing are not written anywhere. But in other excerpts, this work is given the above title.

Akhmed Donish's philosophical analysis of state management and political government affairs has kept up with the times and has not lost its relevance to this day. For example, Donish described Amir Daniyal in his pamphlet "A Brief History of Bukhara Mangites": "In the last years of his reign, he distanced himself from state affairs and gave power to his sons so that they would not observe that he was conducting his administration based on Sharia laws. and distributed to regional governors. Amir Daniel's sons betrayed him. "Also, the never-ending, disparate taxes naturally fell on the ordinary, hardworking people," he tries to show the basis of the state's decline. However, it should also be noted that Ahmad Donish did not live in the time of Amir Daniyal, so he obtained this information from the works of historians and thinkers who lived before him.

In addition, Ahmad Donish gave information about Amir Shahmurad in the introduction of this work and said, "Renovators of religion come to the world every millennium and centenary. During the renewal period of the religion every hundred years, the first fifty years will be a rapid development and the religion will be

strengthened. In the remaining fifty years, there is a backsliding from religion. Therefore, the renovator of this twelfth century is Amir Ma'sum - Amir Shahmurad. At the same time, in the history of Movarounnahr, starting from Amir Temur, he mentions the names of "renovators of religion" every hundred years.

Ahmad Donish, in his pamphlet "Brief History of Bukhara Mangites", critically covered the political processes during the era of Emir Muzaffar and revealed the chaos in the country's administrative management. For example, people named Sherali, Yaqub, Muhammadshah, Durbin, Salimbiy, Barotbek, who studied with the emir, organized their own groups and occupied high positions in the Bukhara Emirate, where they rose to power. regretfully reports that lawlessness and violence have escalated in the country and caused the discontent of the people.

Ahmed Donish admitted that during the reign of Emir Muzaffar, who took the throne of Bukhara from Karmana, oppression in the country increased, farmers were taxed heavily, and no one heard the people's complaints, which is why the decline of the country accelerated.

In the first years of Amir Muzaffar's rule, he gathered an army from the property left by his father and marched to Hisar and Kokhan and occupied several places by force. Disobedient citizens are executed or captured. Proud of this success, the emir tries to subjugate Sharia laws to his will, not recognizing anyone but himself. People are imprisoned even for minor violations, the minimum term of imprisonment is from three to seven years. People were thrown into prison for any small crime. In this way, the dungeons were filled with prisoners, and in order to free the dungeon, they took the prisoners out of the dungeon and executed them in groups. Especially during the time of the emir's father, the emir used to kill people loyal to Nasrullah and appropriate their property. He separated the common people and the slaves from the beginning. Ahmed Donish, who saw these events with his own eyes, expressed his opinion saying "Amir Muzaffar is stupid and short-sighted...", "During the reign of this mindless and bloodthirsty emir...".

Mirza Abdulazim Sami, unlike Ahmad Donish, was afraid to express his thoughts openly, "During the early period of Amir Muzaffar's rule, he wore the robe of justice and generosity. He treated other citizens of the country with amirs and soldiers with various gifts and was kind to them. "He had praiseworthy and good-natured qualities," he said.

Ahmad Donish openly explained the guilt of the emir, Tsarist Russia, and the khanates in the decline of the country. Ahmad Donish expressed his opinion about the occupation of the Khanate by the side of Tsarist Russia, and said that when Tashkent was under siege by the Russians, Amir Muzaffar marched to Kogan, "It is shameful and shameful to oppose the Russians. "If I go against them, I will go

straight to Moscow on my horse," he said with surprise. As a result, as a result of the emir's rash march to Kokhan, Tashkent was easily lost. He spends one hundred thousand coins and twenty months from the treasury to build a protective wall as a border from Bukhara to Jizzakh so that the Russians do not threaten the territories of the Bukhara Emirate. Jizzakh stationed a number of troops around him and appointed Yaqub Qushbegi, who had never heard a gunshot in his life, had absolutely no knowledge of the military, and had never seen a battlefield, as the defense commander. As a result, he notes that soon Samarkand easily fell into the hands of the Russians.

Due to the wrong decision of the emir, an order was given to build fortress walls around Jizzakh, and military garrisons were established, as if to stop the Russian troops. The appointment of Yaqub Kushbegi, who had never heard a gunshot in his life, as the commander-in-chief worsened the situation. The soldiers were also ashamed to fight with such a leader. But while the thinker dwells on the occupation of the Bukhara Emirate in this way, he does not mention the military clashes between the Bukhara and Russian troops, especially the clashes in Kattakurgan, Panjshambe and Zirabulok.

In his treatise, Ahmad Donish discusses the disturbances in the emirate during the reign of Amir Daniyal, the management system of Amir Shahmurad, some events during the reign of Amir Haidar, the reign of Amir Husayn, Amir Umar, one of Amir Haidar's sons, Amir Nasrullah's seizure of power, Amir Muzaffar's management methods and highlights some events during the reign of Amir Abdulahad Khan.

Ahmad Donish's two works are mainly devoted to the problems of history and state administration. This is, first of all, Nawadir-ul-Waqe, which is the main and most important part of the "Political treatise", and "it takes the first place both in terms of the time of its creation and in terms of its importance. "Nawadir-ul-Waqe" occupies the main place among the chapters, and the topic in it is one of the main reasons that prompted the thinker to write the entire book. Secondly, the Treatise is a historical source for the period in which the thinker lived.

Adabiyotlar

1. Ахмад .Дониш. История мангитской династий. Перевод, предисловие и примечание И.А.Наджафовой. Д.1967. - С.43.
2. Епифанова Л.М. Неофициальная версия истории Бухары Мирзи Абдулазима Сами. Автореферат кандидатской диссертации. С.10-11. А.Дониш. История мангитской династий. Перевод, предисловие и примечание И.А.Наджафовой. Д.1967. - С.43.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-6

3. Zebiniso A. Akhmedova, . (2023). PATRIOTIC AND LEGAL EDUCATION IN THE TEACHINGS OF AHMAD DONISH. Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Research Fundamentals, 3(10), 63–66. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/jsshrf/article/view/25588>
4. Akhmedova, Z. A. (2023). HISTORICAL, RELIGIOUS, AND PHILOSOPHICAL IDEAS OF AHMAD DONISH. Mental Enlightenment Scientific-Methodological Journal, 4(04), 254–257. <https://doi.org/10.37547/mesmj-V4-I4-37>
5. Akhmedova Z. A. THE PROBLEM OF HUMAN EXISTENCE AND THE PROBLEM OF NATURE IN THE PHILOSOPHY OF AHMAD DONISH //Oriental Journal of Social Sciences. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 03. – С. 53-58.
6. Akhmedova Z. A. INNOVATIVE IDEAS (FOR HIS ERA) OF THE THINKER AHMAD DONISH //Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Research Fundamentals. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 05. – С. 101-104.
7. Akhmedova Z. A. THE CONTRIBUTION OF AHMAD DONISH TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF EDUCATION IN THE EMIRATE OF BUKHARA //The American Journal of Political Science Law and Criminology. – 2023. – Т. 5. – №. 04. – С. 64-72.
8. Akhmedova Z. A. PHILOSOPHY IN THE WORK OF AKHMAD DONISH //Oriental Journal of History, Politics and Law. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 04. – С. 29-35.
9. Akhmedova Z. A. Socio-Philosophical Views Of Ahmad Donish And His Role In The Formation Of National Ideology //Journal of Positive School Psychology. – 2022. – Т. 6. – №. 8. – С. 2858-2865.
10. Akhmedova Z. A. Reformist views of Ahmad Donish in the renewal of the education system in the Emirate of Bukhara (XIX and Early XX centuries) //American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 03. – С. 1-8.
11. Azizovna A. Z. Spiritual and moral values in the views and activities of Ahmad Donish //European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 06. – С. 174-178.
12. Akhmedova Z. A. PHILOSOPHY OF THE FIRST JADID AHMAD MAHDUM DONISH //CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 12. – С. 41-44.
13. Ахмедова З. А. XIX АСРНИНГ ИККИНЧИ ЯРМИДА ТУРКИСТОН ЎЛКАСИ МАДАНИЯТИ //ВЗГЛЯД В ПРОШЛОЕ. – 2021. – Т. 4. – №. 7.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-6

14. Azizovna A. Z. Culture of Turkestan in the second half of the 19 century //Berlin Studies Transnational Journal of Science and Humanities. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 1.5 Pedagogical sciences.
15. Сагикызы А., Шуршитбай М., Ахмедова З. Upbringing and Education as Factors of Human Capital Development //Адам әлемі. – 2021. – Т. 88. – №. 2. – С. 18-25.
16. Akhmedova Z. A. AHMAD DONISH'S IDEAS ON IMPROVING PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION //Oriental Journal of Philology. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 2. – С. 9-17.
17. Akhmedova Z. A. ANALYSIS BY AHMAD DONISH ABOUT THE STATE ADMINISTRATION OF THE MANGYT RULERS //CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 12. – С. 122-129.
18. Azizovna A. Z. THE ROLE OF TEACHING PHILOSOPHY IN MEDICAL UNIVERSITY //Наука, техника и образование. – 2021. – №. 6 (81). – С. 44-48.

